

Measurement of uniaxially anisotropic dielectrics with a Fabry-Perot open resonator in the 20-50 GHz range

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Abstract—Measurement results of uniaxially anisotropic materials performed with the aid of a plano-concave Fabry-Perot open resonator in the 20-50 GHz frequency range are presented and discussed in this paper. It is shown that a linear polarization of Gaussian modes applied in the characterization allows extracting in-plane complex permittivity of such materials as crystals and foils in a single measurement cycle. It is also shown that dielectric losses exhibit anisotropy, which can be quite significant, like in the sapphire, or relatively small, like in polymer foils.

Index Terms—anisotropy, dielectrics, Fabry-Perot open resonator, microwaves.

I. INTRODUCTION

MICROWAVE characterization of dielectrics with the aid of a Fabry-Perot open resonator (FPOR) has been known for many decades [1]-[3]. This technique exploits the presence of Gaussian modes in the FPOR, which can be perturbed by the insertion of a dielectric sheet with the unknown complex permittivity. The advantage of this technique over widely-recognized methods based on dielectric resonators (DR) [4] is mainly in the combination of large accuracy of resonant methods with their use in a broad frequency bandwidth reaching 110 GHz and beyond. Recent developments related to the automation of the measurement and the use of rigorous, yet, computationally efficient, electromagnetic modelling methods, have made the method one of the most commonly used techniques applicable to the characterization of dielectric sheets at frequencies reaching 110 GHz [5]-[7].

In addition to the aforementioned properties of the FPOR, the sample can be exposed in the resonator to a linearly polarized mode, so in-plane anisotropy of the material can be measured [8]. The aim of this paper is to present measurement results of a few uniaxially-anisotropic materials obtained in the 20-50 GHz range, which have never been presented in the

literature before. The anisotropy of sapphire and quartz crystals is usually presented in the literature as measured with the DR technique at discrete frequencies for the samples with the optical crystallographic axis normal to the surface of the sample. Consequently, the sample is in-plane isotropic and, as such, can be characterized with a split-post DR [9], whereas the out-of-plane permittivity component is characterized with the aid of whispering gallery modes excited in the sample itself [10]. The FPOR can be used to determine these two permittivity components in a single measurement run. For that purpose, however, a different crystallographic orientation of the dielectric sheet made of a given crystal was chosen in order to obtain in-plane anisotropy of the sample. It is also shown in this paper that in-plane anisotropy can be observed in, what seems to be non-intuitive at first glance, polymer foils, indicating some issues occurring in the manufacturing process.

II. MEASUREMENTS

Measurement of the complex permittivity of the material under test (MUT) with the FPOR is usually undertaken using $TEM_{0,0,q}$ modes, where q is a longitudinal mode order. Spatial distribution of the amplitude of the EM field corresponding to these modes can be represented with a Gaussian function, whereas polarization of the EM field in the empty FPOR depends mostly on the coupling method. In this paper, a plano-concave (PC) FPOR, as shown schematically in Fig 1, is exploited [11]. Couplers made of 1.0-mm coaxial lines terminated with tiny magnetic loops are protruding through the holes made in both of the mirrors. Due to the fact that the loops are aligned, a linear polarization of Gaussian modes is excited. Consequently, the FPOR can be applied in the measurement of the in-plane anisotropy of materials provided that the sample is located at a Gaussian beam waist or in its close vicinity, where no longitudinal electric field components are present.

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Extraction of the complex permittivity of the MUT has been undertaken by comparing raw measurement results with look-up tables of the resonance frequencies, as computed with the scattering matrix method (SMM) [6]. Insertion of the in-plane anisotropic material into the FPOR with arbitrary horizontal orientation usually ends up with mode splitting, namely, two resonance curves present relatively close to each other. Therefore, the sample has to be in-plane rotated up to a point when only a single resonance curve, corresponding to one of in-plane permittivity components, is present in a transmission spectrum [8]. It implies that the measurement has to be undertaken twice for two orthogonal orientations of the sample.

Fig. 1. PC FPOR ($D = 100$ mm, $R = 150$ mm, $D_{ap} = 200$ mm) loaded with the sample with the thickness, t , shifted from a planar mirror by a given distance, ds . Numbers denote individual sections of the FPOR applied in the SMM.

At first, an R-cut sapphire sample ($t = 115.4 \pm 1.2$ μm) will be considered. It should be noted that the most common crystallographic orientation of that material in the use for electronic purposes is the C-cut sapphire, which can be represented with the following uniaxial permittivity tensor:

$$\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{\perp} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \epsilon_{\perp} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \epsilon_{\parallel} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The R-plane is inclined $\theta = 57.5667^\circ$ with respect to the C-axis, so the corresponding permittivity tensor can be computed as follows:

$$\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_R = \bar{R}^T \bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_C \bar{R} = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{\perp} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos^2(\theta)\epsilon_{\perp} + \sin^2(\theta)\epsilon_{\parallel} & 0.5\sin(2\theta)(\epsilon_{\parallel} - \epsilon_{\perp}) \\ 0 & 0.5\sin(2\theta)(\epsilon_{\parallel} - \epsilon_{\perp}) & \sin^2(\theta)\epsilon_{\perp} + \cos^2(\theta)\epsilon_{\parallel} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\bar{R} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) \\ 0 & \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

is the rotation matrix.

Fig. 2. (top) Dielectric constant measured with the FPOR for the R-cut sapphire sample ($t = 115.4 \pm 1.2$ μm) in two orthogonal in-plane directions and the out-of-plane Dk component computed using (1)-(3). Error bars are due to thickness uncertainty. (bottom) Loss tangent directly measured for the lower in-plane Dk component and transformed using (1)-(3) to the out-of-plane component. Red dots indicate measurement results obtained for the C-cut sapphire sample, as in [10].

It can be noted that the R-cut sapphire is no longer uniaxially anisotropic. Assuming that the sample is not exposed to the electric field component normal to its surface, the crystal behaves as the bi-axial anisotropic material. The first in-plane permittivity component is unaffected by the rotation of the crystallographic axis, whereas the second component is a weighted mean of the in- and out-of-plane permittivity tensor components of the C-cut sapphire.

Figure 2 shows the obtained results. Both in-plane Dk components are almost non-dispersive (on average: $\epsilon_{\perp,R1,avg} = 9.401$, $\epsilon_{\perp,R2,avg} = 10.891$) with the anisotropy ratio at the level of 1.158. The uncertainty of the measurement at the level of ca.

± 0.1 (<1%), as indicated with error bars, is due to thickness variation. Due to the fact that in the literature there is missing any relevant data that can be used in the validation of the obtained results, it will be compared against widely studied C-cut sapphire, which requires the use of (1)-(3) to get the out-of-plane Dk component (see purple solid line in Figure 2), which is equal on average to $\epsilon_{\parallel} = 11.492$. Comparing against [10], it can be noted that the in-plane Dk component (on average: $\epsilon_{\perp,R1,avg} = 9.401$) is almost the same as measured with a dielectric resonator operating on whispering gallery modes at 21.4 GHz (see red dot in Figure 2). However, the out-of-plane Dk component is about 0.8% less than that in [10], which is still within uncertainty bars plotted in Fig. 2. The obtained discrepancy corresponds to the rotation angle of 2.22° less than the expected one.

Fig. 3. Dielectric constant measured with the FPOR for the X-cut quartz sample ($t = 530 \mu\text{m}$) in two orthogonal in-plane directions. Red dots indicate measurement results obtained for the Z-cut quartz sample, as in [10].

Fig. 4. (a) Dielectric constant and (b) loss tangent of PET foil ($t = 100 \mu\text{m}$).

Figure 2 also presents the in- and out-of-plane loss tangents of the C-cut sapphire, as compared with the reference results [10]. It can be noted that really good agreement has been obtained with both loss tangents increasing linearly with frequency. The loss factor is slightly less for the out-of-plane polarization of the electric field.

Figure 3 shows a Dk measured for the X-cut quartz sample, which also exhibits in-plane anisotropy. It can be noted that the Dk is almost non-dispersive (on average: $\epsilon_{\perp,avg} = 4.432$, $\epsilon_{\parallel,avg} = 4.648$), as in case of sapphire, with the anisotropy ratio at the level of 1.048. The discrepancy, as compared to [10] (see red dots in Figure 3), is at the level of merely -0.2% and 0.08%, respectively.

The last material to be presented in this paper is PET foil, which is manufactured using thermal drawing in two in-plane directions with substantially different draw ratios followed by crystallization under tension at large temperatures. If the process is poorly calibrated, crystallization will be substantially different in two directions leading to the anisotropy of the in-plane complex permittivity, as shown in Fig. 4. It can be observed that in-plane Dk components are 3.184 and 2.976 at ca. $f = 20.67$ GHz, and slightly fall down to 3.163 and 2.956, respectively, at ca. $f = 49.12$ GHz. Consequently, the anisotropy ratio is at the level of ca. 1.069, which is larger than in case of the X-cut quartz. Anisotropy of the loss tangent is much smaller and slightly increases with frequency from 5×10^{-3} up to 5.8×10^{-3} in the 20-50 GHz range. It should be noted that, on the contrary, PETG films are non-crystalline co-polyesters and, as a result, do not exhibit anisotropy [5].

III. CONCLUSION

It has been shown in this paper that the plano-concave FPOR is applicable in the characterization of uniaxially anisotropic dielectric sheets in the 20-50 GHz range. It requires Gaussian modes to be linearly polarized, whereas the sample has to be appropriately oriented so that the mode splitting is not present. The accuracy of the method has been confirmed against alternative methods based on dielectric resonators. It has been shown that the anisotropy of crystals is manifested not only in the dielectric constant but even more in the loss tangent. In case of polymer foils, anisotropy can be the figure of merit of the quality of the manufacturing process but the discrepancy in the loss tangent is not that large as in crystals.

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